

Relationship Between Attendance Rate and Academic Performance of ALS Learners and its Challenges Among ALS Teachers in DepEd Lipa City

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Abstract

The study assessed the relationship between attendance rate and academic performance of ALS learners and its challenges among ALS teacher in DepEd Lipa City.

The researcher employed both quantitative and qualitative method of research design, whereby a careful analysis of the gathered data is made to arrive at the needed answers to the problems posited in the study. The respondents of the study are 30 ALS learners and 13 ALS teachers in Division of Lipa City school year 2024-2025. A survey questionnaire was used as the primary data gathering instrument of the study. The self-made questionnaire was subjected to content validation by the jury of experts. The study revealed that the attendance rate manifested by the learners are classroom learning, student social and emotional support, student-teacher and teacher-family relationship. Among the performance rate of ALS learners presented in the study, student related factors, school related factors, home related factors, and teacher related factors. Academic performance of the learner's attendance rate which includes academic grades, academic performance and success. The challenges ALS teacher in Lipa City includes the following, perceived challenges with students attendance and impact on teaching and learning.

The researcher formulated a proposed activities to enhance the attendance rate and academic performance of ALS learners. This will guide the teacher and the parents in dealing with learners with attendance rate and academic performance of ALS learners. Moreover, it will be helpful for the teachers to address the challenges they encountered.

Additionally, the future researchers may conduct further studies on the relationship between of attendance rate and academic performance of ALS learners and the challenges encountered among ALS teacher.

Keywords: *attendance rate, academic performance, challenges, Lipa City*

Introduction

The Alternative Learning System (ALS) is a parallel learning system in the Philippines that provides a practical option to the existing formal instruction. It is primarily designed for individuals who do not have access to formal education, including out-of-school youth, adults, and those with special learning needs. It is also applicable to those learners who are willing to pursue and finish their education even though they have work. In other words, Alternative Learning System (ALS) are generally refers to any educational approach outside the traditional classroom model.

This study deals with the causes of the learner's attendance rate and academic rate of ALS learners and the challenges encountered by the teachers in ALS Lipa City. More specifically, it answers the following questions:

1. What is the status of attendance rate of ALS learners as to the following:
 - 1.1 Classroom Learning
 - 1.2 Student Social and Emotional Support
 - 1.3 Student-Teacher and Teacher-Family Relationship
2. What is the status of performance rate of ALS learners in terms of the following:
 - 2.1 Student Related
 - 2.2 School Related
 - 2.3 Home Related
 - 2.4 Teacher Related
3. To what extent is the academic performance affected by the learners attendance rate in following;
 - 3.1 Academic grades
 - 3.2 Academic Performance
 - 3.3 Success
4. What are the different challenges encountered by ALS teacher?
 - 4.1 Perceived Challenges with students attendance
 - 4.2 Impact on Teaching and Learning
5. Based on the findings, what enhancement activities make proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

The research design used for this study was a mixed method of research, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative approaches. This research procedure was designed to gather data and information regarding the existing conditions that will serve as bases for the evaluation procedure that follows. It involved the collection of facts in order to answer questions related to the nature of the study being pursued.

Participants

The respondents of the study were 30 ALS learners in Lipa City and 13 ALS teachers in the Division of Lipa City school year 2024-2025. They were selected based on attendance rate and the objective of the study.

Research Instruments

The study used the questionnaire as one of the basic instruments in finding answers to the different problems discussed in this study. Data were obtained by the use of two categories of questionnaires for teachers and registered learners in ALS in Lipa City. These questionnaires contained close-ended questions.

- **Construction of Questionnaire.** The main instrument used in gathering data was the research-made questionnaire. The research engaged in library research and internet to gather different materials relevant to the study.
- **Validation of Questionnaire.** The content of the questionnaire was presented to the research adviser prior to the questionnaire development.
- **Administration of the Questionnaire.** After the questionnaire has been finalized and permit to distribute the questionnaire has been granted, it was then administered to the intended respondents.

Data Collection Procedure

To obtain the result of the study, the research had prepared letters for the ALS Focal person in Lipa City and for the respondent for their approval. Tabulation of the gathered data from the teachers and ALS learners as respondents of the study was done by the researcher, and computation was done by the expert.

Data Analysis

The following statistical procedures were used in analyzing and interpreting the data gathered from the teachers and learner-respondents.

- Frequency count.
- Weighted mean
- Composite mean
- Ranking

Results

Section 1: Attendance Rate of ALS Learners

Legend Table 1-3:

WM= Weighted Mean VI = Verbal Interpretation R = Rank
 SA = Strongly Agree A= Agree D=Disagree SD= Strongly Disagree

Table 1: Classroom Learning.

INDICATORS	WM	VI	R
1. I attend class more frequently when teachers use resources that reflect students' backgrounds. (<i>mas madalas akong pumapasok sa klase kapag gumagamit ang mga guro ng mga kagamitan na sumasalamain sa aming pinagmulan o kultura</i>)	3.57	SA	3
2. I attend class more frequently when learning includes students' input about what and how topics will be discussed in class. (<i>mas madalas akong pumapasok sa klase kapag isinasaalang-alang sa pagkatuto ang mga suhestiyon o opinyon ng mga estudyante tungkol sa mga paksang tatalakayin at kung paano ito ituturo</i>)	3.63	SA	2
3. I attend class more frequently when teachers make learning more relevant to their daily life. (<i>mas madalas akong pumapasok sa klase kapag ginagawa ng mga guro na may kaugnayan sa aming pang-araw-araw na buhay ang aming pagkatuto</i>)	3.43	A	4
4. I attend class more frequently when teachers provide ways for students to express their opinions. (<i>mas madalas akong pumapasok sa klase kapag nagbibigay ang mga guro ng paraan para maipahayag ng mga estudyante ang kanilang mga opinion</i>)	3.66	SA	1
5. I attend class more frequently when teachers provide opportunities for students to debate. (<i>mas madalas akong pumapasok sa klase kapag nagbibigay ang mga guro ng pagkakataon sa mga estudyante na makipagtalos o makipagdebate</i>)	3.30	A	5
Composite Mean	3.52	SA	

Table 2: Student Social and Emotional Support.

INDICATORS	WM	VI	R
1. I believe that students attend school more frequently when the school provides therapy/trauma-related support services. (<i>naniniwala ako na mas madalas pumapasok ang mga estudyante sa paaralan kapag nagbibigay ito ng mga serbisyo para sa therapy o suporta sa mga nakaranas ng trauma</i>)	3.40	A	3
2. I believe that students go to the nurse when class is overwhelming. (<i>naniniwala ako na pumupunta ang mga estudyante sa clinic kapag labis na nakaka-overwhelm ang klase</i>)	2.87	A	5
3. I believe that students go to the nurse when teachers don't seem to care about them. (<i>naniniwala ako na pumupunta ang mga estudyante sa clinic kapag pakiramdam nila na walang pakialam sa kanila ang mga guro</i>)	3.13	A	4

4. I believe that students are provided with opportunities throughout the school day to identify and express their feelings. (<i>naniniwala ako na binibigyan ang mga estudyante ng mga pagkakataon sa buong maghapon sa paaralan upang matukoy at maipahayag ang kanilang mga nararamdaman</i>)	3.53	SA	2
5. I believe that students have at least one teacher who knows and cares about them. (<i>naniniwala ako na may kahit isang guro ang bawat estudyante na nakakakilala at tunay na nagmamalasakit sa kanila</i>)	3.60	SA	1
Composite Mean	3.31	A	

Table 3: Student-Teacher and Teacher-Family Relationship

INDICATORS	WM	VI	R
1. I am more likely to attend school when students believe teachers are interested in them. (<i>mas malamang na pumasok ako sa paaralan kapag naniniwala ang mga estudyante na interesado sa kanila ang mga guro</i>)	3.60	SA	2
2. I am more likely to attend school when teachers show respect for students. (<i>mas malamang na pumasok ako sa paaralan kapag ipinapakita ng mga guro ang kanilang paggalang sa mga estudyante</i>)	3.63	SA	1
3. I am more likely to attend school when teachers understand students' needs. (<i>mas malamang na pumasok ako sa paaralan kapag naiintindihan ng mga guro ang pangangailangan ng mga estudyante</i>)	3.53	SA	3
4. I am more likely to attend school when teachers encourage students to participate in school activities. (<i>Mas malamang na pumasok ako sa paaralan kapag hinihikayat ng mga guro ang mga estudyante na makilahok sa mga gawain ng paaralan</i>)	3.50	SA	4
5 I am more likely to attend school when teachers attend community events to show support for student's development ¹¹ a2. (<i>Mas malamang na pumasok ako sa paaralan kapag dumadalo ang mga guro sa mga aktibidad sa komunidad bilang suporta sa pag-unlad ng mga estudyante</i>)	3.40	A	5
Composite Mean	3.53	SA	

Section 2: Performance Rate of ALS Learners

Legend Table 4-7:

WM= Weighted Mean VI = Verbal Interpretation R = Rank
A = Always O = Often S = Sometimes R = Rarely

Table 4: Student Related Factors

INDICATORS	WM	VI	R
How well do you listen to your teacher? (<i>Gaano ka kahusay makinig sa iyong guro?</i>)	3.47	O	2
How well do you actively participate in the discussion, answering and clarifying things you did not understand? (<i>Gaano ka kahusay na nakikilahok nang aktibo sa talakayan, sumasagot, at nagtatanong para malinawan sa mga bagay na hindi mo naintindihan?</i>)	3.40	O	3
How well do you want to get good grades on test, quizzes, assignments, and projects? (<i>Gaano mo kagustong makakuha ng mataas na marka sa mga pagsusulit, quizzes, takdang-aralin, at proyekto?</i>)	3.67	A	1
How well do you make yourself prepared for the subject? (<i>Gaano ka kahusay maghanda para sa asignatura?</i>)	3.17	O	4
How well do you get frustrated when discussion is interrupted or the teacher is absent? (<i>Gaano ka kainis o nadidismaya kapag napuputol ang talakayan o kapag wala ang guro?</i>)	2.97	O	5
Composite Mean	3.34	O	

Table 5: School Related Factors

INDICATORS	WM	VI	R
How well do you use the learning facilities provided by the university (library, computer laboratory, and chalkboard)? (<i>Gaano mo kahusay ginagamit ang mga pasilidad sa pagkatuto na ibinibigay ng unibersidad (aklatan, computer laboratory, at pisara)?</i>)	3	O	3
How well do you use the learning facilities in performing our course work? (<i>Gaano mo kahusay ginagamit ang mga pasilidad sa pagkatuto sa paggawa ng mga gawain sa kurso?</i>)	3.17	O	2
How well do you think the facilities provided by the university meet the standards for physical requirement (classroom size, lighting, air conditioning, tables, and chairs)? (<i>Sa iyong palagay, gaano kahusay natutugunan ng mga pasilidad na ibinibigay ng unibersidad ang mga pamantayan sa pisikal na pangangailangan (laki ng silid-aralan, ilaw, air conditioning, mga mesa, at upuan)?</i>)	3.40	O	1
How well do you can easily access the internet in the library? (<i>Gaano kadali para sa iyo ang makagamit ng internet sa aklatan?</i>)	2.93	A	4
How well do you adhere to the “Speak English Policy” of the university? (<i>Gaano ka kahusay sumunod sa ‘Speak English Policy’ ng unibersidad?</i>)	2.73	O	5
Composite Mean	3	O	

Table 6: Home Related Factors

INDICATORS	WM	VI	R
Are you motivated by your parents to improve your studies? <i>(Hinihikayat ka ba ng iyong mga magulang na pagbutihin ang iyong pag-aaral?)</i>	3.40	O	2
Do you use your learning materials (book, dictionary, and laptop) suitable for your learning? <i>(Ginagamit mo ba ang iyong mga learning materials (aklat, diksyunaryo, at laptop) nang naaayon sa iyong pagkatuto?)</i>	3.53	A	1
Do you have tutorial sessions after class? <i>(Mayroon ka bang tutorial sessions pagkatapos ng klase?)</i>	2.93	O	4
Do you easily get distracted by your friends? <i>(Madali ka bang nadidistract o naaabala ng iyong mga kaibigan?)</i>	3.07	O	3
Do your mobile phone/television/radio/gadgets distract you while studying your lesson? <i>(Nakakaabala ba sa iyo ang iyong cellphone/telebisyon/radyo/ gadgets habang nag-aaral ka ng iyong leksyon?)</i>	2.40	S	5
Composite Mean	3.07	O	

Teacher Related Factors

INDICATORS	WM	VI	R
Do your teachers have a good relationship with the student and co-teacher? <i>(Mayroon ba ang iyong mga guro ng maayos na relasyon sa mga estudyante at kapwa guro?)</i>	3.61	A	3
Do your teachers impose proper discipline and are not lenient in following the prescribed rules? <i>(Ipinapatupad ba ng iyong mga guro ang tamang disiplina at hindi sila pabaya sa pagpapatupad ng mga itinakdang alituntunin)</i>	3.47	O	5
Do your teachers open to suggestion and opinion and is worthy of praise? <i>(Bukas ba ang iyong mga guro sa mga suhestiyon at opinyon at karapat-dapat silang purihin?)</i>	3.60	A	4
Do your teachers show smartness, confidence, and firmness in making decision? <i>(Ipinapakita ba ng iyong mga guro ang talino, kumpiyansa sa sarili, at katatagan sa paggawa ng desisyon?)</i>	3.70	A	1
Do your teachers have an appealing personality with good sense of humor? <i>(May kaaya-aya bang personalidad ang iyong mga guro at may magandang sense of humor?)</i>	3.63	A	2
Composite Mean	3.61	A	

Section 3: Academic Performance of the Learner's Attendance Rate

Legend Table 8-10:

WM= Weighted Mean VI = Verbal Interpretation R = Rank VGE= Very Great Extent
GE = Great Extent NE = Normal Extent LE = limited Extent

Table 8: Academic Grades

INDICATORS	WM	VI	R
1. Do you believe that showing up on class will make your grades higher? <i>(Naniniwala ka ba na ang pagpasok sa klase ay makakatulong upang tumaas ang iyong marka?)</i>	3.23	GE	3
2. Do you adhere that being present in class puts you in a good rank inside the classroom? <i>(Sang-ayon ka ba na ang pagiging present sa klase ay nagbibigay sa iyo ng magandang ranggo sa loob ngsilid-aralan?)</i>	3.53	VGE	1
3. Do you prefer to be at school just to maintain your grades? <i>(Mas gusto mo bang pumasok sa paaralan para lamang mapanatili ang iyong mga marka?)</i>	3.37	GE	2
4. Do you believe that your attendance has something to do with your grades? <i>(Naniniwala ka ba na may kinalaman ang iyong pagdalo sa klase sa iyong mga marka?)</i>	3.16	GE	4
5. Do you think being away from school tend to lower someone's grade? <i>(Sa palagay mo ba, ang madalas na pagliban sa paaralan ay nakakapagbaba ng marka ng isang estudyante?)</i>	3.03	GE	5
Composite Mean	3.26	GE	

Table 9: Academic Performance

INDICATORS	WM	VI	R
1. Does class attendance the self-efficiency of a student towards the better performance? <i>(Nakakaapekto ba ang pagdalo sa klase sa tiwala ng estudyante sa sarili tungo sa mas mahusay na pagganap?)</i>	3.2	NE	5
2. Does being present in the class improve someone's intelligence? <i>(Nakakapagpatalino ba ang palaging pagpasok sa klase?)</i>	3.4	NE	3
3. Does class attendance somehow related to the level of competence exhibited by the students? <i>(May kaugnayan ba ang pagdalo sa klase sa antas ng kakayahan na ipinapakita ng mga estudyante?)</i>	3.93	GE	1
4. Does being regularly present at school enhance someone's social interaction? <i>(Nakakatulong ba ang regular na pagpasok sa paaralan upang mapabuti ang pakikisalamuha ng isang tao?)</i>	3.6	GE	2
5. Does class attendance plays an integral part about the learning outcomes of students? <i>(May mahalagang bahagi ba ang pagpasok sa klase sa mga kinalalabasan ng pagkatuto ng mga estudyante?)</i>	3.33	NE	4
Composite Mean	3.49	GE	

Table 10: Success

INDICATORS	WM	VI	R
1. Do you think the academic performance can predict your possible success? <i>(Sa tingin mo ba, ang iyong akademikong pagganap ay makakapagpahiwatig ng posibleng tagumpay mo sa hinaharap?)</i>	3.07	GE	4.5
2. Does having good records of attendance gives you academic achievements? <i>(Ang pagkakaroon ba ng magandang rekord ng pagpasok sa klase ay nagbibigay ng mga akademikong tagumpay?)</i>	3.40	GE	2
3. Does the exhibited performance of the learner determine his/her future success? <i>(Ang ipinakitang pagganap ba ng mag-aaral ay tumutukoy sa magiging tagumpay niya sa hinaharap?)</i>	3.27	GE	3
4. Do you think the present performance in school can affect your employment status in the future? <i>(Sa palagay mo ba, maaapektuhan ng kasalukuyan mong pagganap sa paaralan ang magiging trabaho mo balang araw?)</i>	3.07	GE	4.5
5. Does being regularly present in school will manifest on your performance within the class? <i>(Ang pagiging palaging present ba sa paaralan ay makikita sa iyong pagganap sa klase?)</i>	3.50	VGE	1
Composite Mean	3.26	GE	

Section 4: Challenges ALS Teacher in Lipa City

Legend Table 11-12:

WM= Weighted Mean VI = Verbal Interpretation R = Rank SA= Strongly Agree
A= Agree N = Neutral D = Disagree SD = Strongly Disagree

Table 11: Perceived Challenges with Students Attendance

INDICATORS	WM	VI	R
1. Student absences negatively impact learning environment	1.4	SD	2
2. Student absences hinder my ability to effectively each.	1.33	SD	3.5
3. Student absences affect student engagement.	1.33	SD	3.5
4. Student absences impact my own workload.	1.67	D	1
Composite Mean	1.14	SD	

Table 12: **Impact on Teaching and Learning**

INDICATORS	WM	VI	R
1.Student achievement	1.4	NA	2
2.Student progress	1.27	NA	4
3.Classroom participation	1.47	LE	1
4.Overall class performance	1.33	NA	3
Composite Mean	1.37	NA	

Section 5:

The Proposed Activities to Enhance the Attendance Rate and Academic Performance of ALS Learners are the following:

- Regular Monitoring and Tracking of Attendance and Performance
- Providing Incentives for Good Attendance
- Peer Tutoring and Mentoring Programs
- Strengthening Engagement and Interaction
- Parent and Community involvement
- Flexible Learning Schedules
- Catch-up Sessions for Absent Learners
- Use of Technology and E-Learning Tools

Discussion

1. Table 1 showed that classroom learning has a total composite mean of 3.52 which is Strongly Agree. The indicator with highest weighted mean is 3.66 attend class more frequently when teacher provide ways for students to express their opinion

2.The attendance of ALS learners in terms of student social and emotion support has a composite mean of 3.31 signifies that student social and emotional support is exhibited by learner at “Agree”.

3.Table 3 showed that ALS learners most likely attend their class when teacher show respect for students with weighted mean of 3.63 which is Strongly Agree. The composite mean of 3.53 Strongly Agree.

4.Table 4 showed ALS performance rate in terms of student related factors has composite mean of 3.34 which is exhibited by leaners “Often”

5. The composite mean of 3.0 signifies that school related factors is exhibited by learners at Often.

6. The composite mean of 3.07 signifies that home related factors is exhibited by learners at “ Often”. With highest weighted mean of 3.53 shows that the learners use learning materials suitable for learning at “Always”.

7. Table 7 showed ALS learners' performance are based when teacher show smartness, confidence, and firmness in making decision with weighted mean of 3.70 at "Always". The composite mean of 3.61 signifies that home related factors is exhibited by learners at "Always".

8. The composite mean of 3.26 signifies that student related factors is exhibited by learners at "Great Extent".

9. Table 9 shows the academic performance of the learner's attendance rate in terms of academic performance with the composite mean of 3.49 which is exhibited by learners at "Great Extent".

10. Table 10 showed the composite mean of 3.26 signifies that academic performance of the learner's attendance rate in term of success at Great Extent.

11. The challenges among the ALS teacher in terms of perceived challenges with student attendance has composite mean of 1.14 signifies that students related factors is exhibited by learners at "Strongly Disagree".

12. Table 12 shows that challenges among the ALS teacher in terms of impact on teaching and learning with the composite mean of 1.37 signifies that the related factors is exhibited by learners at "None All"

Conclusion

The following conclusions had been drawn from the findings and interpretations of the study.

1. The status of attendance rate of the learners exhibits classroom learning by attend class more frequently when teachers provide opportunities for students to debate, because debate can make learning more engaging and interactive encourage student to participate actively, share their thoughts, and develop critical thinking skills.

2. In terms of student social and emotional support, students go to the nurse or clinic when class is overwhelming. The nurses might offer a listening ear and emotional support, the nurse's office can provide calm environment, and they can help students to manage stress.

3. For student-teacher and teacher-family relationship learners are more likely to attend school when teachers show respect for students because respectful teachers build trust and positive relationships. Students feel valued and safe, respect boost students' confidence and motivation.

4. The performance rate of ALS learners in terms of student related factors shows that they got frustrated when discussion is interrupted or the teacher is absent, because interruption can disrupt their train of thoughts, absence can cause confusion and disrupt lesson continuity. Learners may feel their questions or concerns aren't addressed. On the other hand, school related factors "English Speaking Policy" adhere a lot in the ALS learners because English is often a common language and improves proficiency.

5. In home related factors, learners have tutorial session after class because it is an additional help in challenging topics, they can review and practice, clarify doubts and get answer. For teacher related factors says that teacher is open for the suggestion and opinion and worthy of praise because learners feel heard and valued and it motivates learners and enhances their learning experience

6. In terms of academic performance of learner's attendance rate, learners believe that their attendance has something to do with their academic grades because regular attendance allows them to participate and cooperate in class discussion and engage with the material. They believe that absences can result in missed lesson, assignments and opportunities to learn. In academic performance, learner learned that attendance is somehow related to the level of competence because regular attendance helps learner consistently practice and reinforce their skills.

7. Learner thinks that the present performance in school can affect employment status in the future because good performance helps develop skills and knowledge that are valuable in the job market.

8. The challenges among ALS teachers in Lipa City in terms of student's attendance shows that student absences may impact their workload. They believe that absent students may need extra support to catch up on missed material, provide additional support outside the class and adjust their lesson plans to accommodate absent students. On the other hand, the impact on teaching and learning is on classroom participation because helps teacher tailor instruction and supports students academic success.

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